

Best Practices

Teaching, learning, and organising in an informal, urban astronomy movement: Describing a non-hierarchical, democratic #popscope pedagogy and practice

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This article theorises a #popscope pedagogy and practice that describes the teaching, learning, and organising that occur in an informal, urban sidewalk astronomy movement. This approach may be seen as a “best practice” that may guide similar urban astronomy outreach initiatives. #popscope is a completely volunteer-run urban astronomy group founded in 2014 that has hosted over 500 events and served more than 20,000 guests in North America and around the world. By democratising astronomical knowledge, strengthening social connectedness, and using public spaces, #popscope shares goals and activities with other sidewalk astronomy events such as “star parties” but with an additional, intentional focus on overlooked urban communities and the creation of non-hierarchical learning spaces. So theorised, #popscope pedagogy and practice comprise many characteristics of informal or free-choice learning, hybrid in-person and online learning, joy-centred learning and teaching, and affinity spaces. “Affinity spaces” (e.g., Gee, 2004), a description of informal, non-hierarchical learning spaces outside of traditional schooling, offer a useful frame for bringing elements of a #popscope pedagogy together. The manuscript relies on the author’s reflections on #popscope activities, as well as analysis of #popscope organisational media and literature. In addition, the article presents counterpoints, such as the limits of equitable astronomy outreach, the risk of science misinformation in informal spaces, and the role of informal learning in the classroom.

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1. Introduction

This article outlines the characteristics of teaching, learning, and organising that take place at #popscope events – in short, a “#popscope pedagogy” and practice.

Drawing connections to educational scholarship and other “best practices” for informal astronomy education, this article references three goals of #popscope, short for “pop-up telescope”, a free, urban astronomy group co-founded by the author with Viva Dadwal in 2014. It shares elements with

other sidewalk astronomy initiatives, and focuses on three mission pillars: 1) democratising astronomy knowledge; 2) building community; and 3) activating public spaces ([#popscope, 2025a](#)). In pursuit of these pillars, the group intentionally focuses on serving urban, often light-polluted, areas that other astronomy outreach groups frequently overlook. Now with chapters in several North American cities, the group has served approximately 20,000 guests at 500 different pop-up astronomy nights over the last decade. Events usually feature a telescope on a busy city street corner or other public, urban spaces ([#popscope, 2025a](#)).

Why explore pedagogy, the “strategies, techniques, and approaches used to facilitate learning” ([O’Leary, 2007, pp. 189–190](#))? As an educator and education researcher, the author is interested in the teaching and learning that takes place in and around #popscope events. There are many ways to theorise the inter-and multi-disciplinary work of #popscope, including science communication (e.g., [Madsen & West, 2003](#)), sidewalk astronomy (e.g., [Pompea & Russo, 2020](#)), informal and free-choice learning (e.g., [Falk et al., 2007](#)), a hobby for astronomers (e.g., [Azevedo, 2019](#)), social astronomy (e.g., [Bará, 2009](#)), or affinity spaces (e.g., [Gee, 2004](#)). This manuscript draws on elements from each of these bodies of research and practice. Just as the field of education draws on many traditions (e.g., sociology and economics), a #popscope pedagogy can be broad and interdisciplinary, considering the democratic nature of outreach events (e.g., political science) alongside the use of digital tools by #popscope organisers, for example (e.g., communications theory).

The word “pedagogy” is intentionally chosen to describe #popscope as it highlights elements that can be applied more broadly to education settings beyond sidewalk astronomy and science education, such as classroom teaching and education research. Using the term pedagogy to help us explore the teaching and learning that takes place around a telescope is an extension of the term to capture the educational experiences that take place out of formal learning environments, like the classroom. Just as other scholars have recognised the learning that takes place through experiential learning ([Dewey, 1916](#)) and in informal or free-choice learning environments (e.g. [Falk et al., 2007](#)), the author joins other scholars in expanding notions of pedagogy and recognising the educational value of other, more informal “third spaces” like sidewalks, courtyards, or kitchen tables (e.g., [Galvan, 2001](#)). This manuscript has similar goals to Azevedo’s research ([2019](#)), which examined the pedagogy of amateur astronomer communities and the structure of their learning and teaching opportunities. Theorising #popscope activities through an education lens also has the potential to “effect educational practice” ([Azevedo, 2019, p. 2](#)) in settings where free-choice or informal learning may be undervalued by teachers and administrators compared to traditional classroom schooling.

The decision of how to organise events and where these events take place pedagogical decisions that shape the teaching and learning experience. How a space is organised will necessarily affect how learners engage with materials and teachers (e.g., [Byers et al., 2014](#)). Thinking about organisation is especially important as #popscope takes place in informal spaces outside a formal classroom environment and that are even less formal than other

informal science sites, such as museums (e.g., [Falk & Dierking, 2010](#)). These spaces also include virtual ones: #popscope activities often continue in online spaces, such as WhatsApp or smart phone-enabled planetarium apps, after and sometimes during, in-person #popscope events.

Over the following pages, the manuscript draws connections between interdisciplinary elements of #popscope's mission and practice with principles of a #popscope pedagogy and practice: equitable astronomy outreach, online learning and digital educational tools, the role of joy in spontaneous public settings, and spaces that exist outside of formal learning spaces. Throughout, connections will be made between the organisation of #popscope, including structure and internal norms, and the teaching and learning that takes place at #popscope activities. Each element of this pedagogy will be discussed in a subsequent section.

As a conceptual piece, this manuscript is based on the author's reflections ([Eberle, 2014](#)) as a co-founder of #popscope and a research-practitioner ([Fox et al., 2007](#)) across a variety of education settings over the last 10 years (including higher education and K-12 settings). These reflections may necessarily differ from those of other #popscope group members. This manuscript also analyses organisational material, such as the group's website and internal documents, including the #popscope volunteer manual. The latter provides a guide for new volunteers to run a successful #popscope event in line with the group's mission and values. The manuscript ends with a reflection on the significance, limitations and future directions for this pedagogical reflection.

2. Informal learning and informal spaces

#popscope, though established independently, is related to other informal teaching and science movements. Firstly, it is an example of informal science teaching (e.g., [Kim & Dopico, 2016](#)). An estimated 95% of science learning among students in the United States takes place outside formal school classroom environments ([Falk & Dierking, 2010](#)). Most science knowledge is acquired outside school in a variety of informal and free-choice learning environments, including museums, zoos, planetaria, libraries (e.g., [Falk & Dierking, 2010](#)), clubs, maker spaces (e.g., [Kjällander et al., 2018](#)), and out-of-school time (OST) programmes (e.g., [Baldrige et al., 2024](#)). To this list we might add the home, talking at the kitchen table, or simply hanging out at the park with friends, looking for beetles, or examining a leaf.

More specifically, #popscope is an example of informal learning and other democratising astronomy movements, such as "sidewalk astronomy" (e.g., [Pompea & Russo, 2020](#)). Sidewalk astronomy was popularised by John Dobson ([Dobson & Sperling, 1991](#)) and his style of low-cost, do-it-yourself, homemade reflector telescopes, often referred to today as "Dobsonian" telescopes. Dobson's telescopes featured home-made mirrors, "discarded hose reels, lumber core cut-outs from schoolhouse doors, and items of scrap wood" ([English, 2018, pp. 627–](#)

628). He founded the Sidewalk Astronomy Club in 1968 in San Francisco to share views of the night sky with the broader public.

Sidewalk astronomy literature is often written by practitioners (e.g., [Erickson & Friedland, 2000](#); [Mackie, 2002](#); [Simmons, 2008](#)), who describe setting up portable telescopes in a variety of informal, public spaces. These locations can include “urban streets, or outside shopping malls or stadiums,” where “a small telescope and its operator can attract multitudes for an exciting view of the Moon or Jupiter” ([Pompea & Russo, 2020, p. 22](#)). Sidewalk astronomy has also been noted for its role in contributing to urban energy and “street vitality in dynamic urban public spaces”, such as in contemporary Singapore ([Yeo et al., 2016, p. 393](#)).

The reaction of passers-by peering through their telescopes is often a primary motivator for sidewalk astronomers, who are usually volunteers. Telescope operators describe the “vicarious reward” of sharing views of Saturn’s rings or the Moon’s craters with eager passersby ([Mackie, 2002, p. 48](#)). Dobson, for example, felt the urge to share his views of a gibbous Moon with a home-made telescope with others ([English, 2018, p. 627](#)). “Most report satisfaction in inspiring excitement and awe in others, a common example being evoking the “ahhhhh” sound heard when people first see Saturn through a telescope,” note Buxner et al. ([2021, p. 147](#)). Similarly, in a 2016 letter to Sky & Telescope, the founders of #popscope describe how they “witness [guests’] screams of delight and cries of disbelief as they see the Moon’s craters, Saturn’s rings, or Jupiter’s moons” ([Dadwal & M. O’Shea, 2016, p. 6](#)).

3. Equitable urban sidewalk astronomy?

The social and community goals of the group (pillars 2 and 3) are as important as its astronomy education goals and contribute to a #popscope that aims to construct and disseminate knowledge collaboratively. Both the selection of event sites and their spontaneous pop-up organisation on busy urban street corners engage populations not reached by other astronomy outreach or informal astronomy institutions (e.g., planetaria). The group also seeks to expand the amateur astronomy community’s reach by empowering first-time stargazers and new members as volunteers, providing them with telescope equipment and support to host their events. Photographs from past events ([#popscope, 2025b](#)) accompany the text to visually demonstrate some elements of #popscope pedagogy ([Figures 1-3](#)). With an eye toward sustained community-rooted relationships beyond ephemeral interactions around a telescope, #popscope has much in common with [Bará’s \(2009\)](#) description of social astronomy, that is, sidewalk astronomy that is coordinated with, and in relationship with, other community groups.

Access and equity are central values to #popscope’s pedagogy and practice: the group is intentional in choosing sites in urban communities that are often overlooked due to light concerns about pollution¹. These communities are frequently racialised and historically underserved communities. [Nadybal \(2020, p. 2\)](#) found that racialised populations across the

United States are generally more exposed to light pollution than White populations in their home communities, even accounting for geographic (e.g., suburban versus rural) differences.

Many informal organisations or amateur astronomers have important and impactful outreach arms that carry out outreach activities, especially star parties. Often, however, the focus is on finding the best dark-sky site to observe fainter dark-sky objects rather than on areas with the greatest need, which are often communities with high levels of light pollution ([Nadybal et al., 2020](#)). Racialised and underserved communities may also experience not only fewer or less-resourced formal educational opportunities (such as public schools), but also fewer informal science opportunities (such as museums; e.g., [Dawson, 2014](#); [Buckland et al., 2020](#)). Avoiding light-polluted neighbourhoods compounds the lack of informal science opportunities in such communities. It may also, in the long term, contribute to the lack of racial and socioeconomic diversity in professional and amateur astronomy.

Under-representation of marginalised populations in the astronomy and physics workforce is indeed well-documented and unfortunately persists despite frequent diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) reports and initiatives (e.g., [Stassun et al., 2010](#); [Ko et al., 2014](#); [TEAM-UP, 2020](#)). Under-representation extends to amateur astronomers, who outnumber professional astronomers by an estimated 10:1 ratio ([Percy, 1998, p. 205](#)). “Today, amateur astronomers in Western societies remain largely Caucasian, well educated, male, and with significant disposable income”, note [Buxner et al. \(2021, p. 144\)](#).

#popscope, in contrast to the outreach focus of many amateur groups, steers toward, not away from, light-polluted urban communities that are frequently also racialised. According to [Buxner et al. \(2021\)](#), #popscope “brings telescopes to urban centres and shares astronomy with many communities who are often left out of or cannot attend other telescope observing events” ([p. 148](#)) and seeks to invite community members to join the group as volunteers. Access and

Figure 1 Founding members of #popscope and friends, Ottawa, Ontario, in 2014. Credit: #popscope collection

Figure 2 Guests gather around the telescope on a busy street corner in Wicker Park, Chicago, IL. Credit: #popscope collection

Figure 3 Baltimore #popscope friends – and some new friends – relax after of night of street corner astronomy and music. Credit: #popscope collection

equity are central to #popscope practice and pedagogy: the group provides telescopes in neighbourhoods that may lack such equipment or informal or free-choice learning opportunities due to patterns of racialised underinvestment and segregation. Providing access to the telescope is every bit as important as giving a view of the night sky.

4. Informal online learning: must #popscope be in person?

While #popscope, as an example of informal science learning (e.g., [Falk et al., 2007](#)), is foremost an in-person activity ([#popscope, 2025a](#)) that connects people around a telescope, it makes extensive use of digital tools such YouTube, WhatsApp, the organisation’s Google Drive and Google Meet, SMS messaging, Zoom, Flickr, virtual smartphone planetarium apps (e.g., Stellarium), and, most recently, online Geographic Information System (GIS) mapping. The group uses these tools for several purposes: learning and teaching (e.g., a mobile planetarium app), sharing and broadcasting experiences (e.g., Instagram), organising volunteers (e.g., WhatsApp), and connecting with the public (e.g., Facebook). A hashtag, a nod to the practice of “tagging” posts on social media platforms like Twitter (now X) and Instagram (e.g., [Zappavigna & Martin, 2018](#)), is also part of the group’s name. Most recently, a volunteer with ASTRO ACCEL, a “network of networks that brings together researchers and practitioners in the domains of

astronomy engagement, communication and culture” ([ASTRO ACCEL, 2024](#)), has transformed records of in-person outreach events into a digital teaching tool by mapping #popscope educational activities from the last 10 years using GIS software ([Crampton, 2011](#)). The result is an interactive GIS map available on the [#popscope website](#) that allows its volunteers to reflect on their activities regarding light pollution and residential segregation patterns to inform future outreach.

How does a movement that’s predicated on in-person, often spontaneous, events interact and reckon with its digital connectedness? To provide additional context for the question, there is a rich body of scholarship on informal online learning to consider. These informal spaces include, for example, YouTube (e.g., [Tan, 2013](#)), social networks (e.g., [Greenhow & Robelia, 2009](#)), and “virtual counter spaces”, such those for Latina graduate students that “support cultural affirmation, community building, knowledge sharing, and empowerment that enable [their academic success]” ([Gomez & Cabrera, 2023, p. 1105](#)).

It may be that #popscope, as an example of informal science education, reflects the hybrid realities of online and offline life and learning that the estimated 5.45 billion Internet users ([Tila, 2025](#)) – a majority of the world’s population, though with varying levels of connectivity (e.g., [Hargittai, 2022](#)) – experience today. [Chayko \(2014\)](#) explores “how digital (online) and face-to-face (offline) spaces become fully integrated and experienced as a single, enmeshed reality” (p. 976). While it is primarily an experiential and educational activity, #popscope has embraced digital tools to mediate and maintain its activities, using WhatsApp to organise sidewalk astronomy events, where guests gather in person to look upward together. When in-person gatherings were not possible during the COVID-19 pandemic, volunteers came together on Zoom to watch online content, specifically the 2021 livestream of the NASA Perseverance mission landing on Mars ([National Aeronautics and Space Administration, 2021](#)).

Another way to think about the hybrid nature of #popscope events is that they are multimodal, engaging learners to “call upon many meaning-making systems and technologies” that may be “linguistic, visual, spatial, gestural, and audio” ([Ryan et al., 2010, p. 478](#)). They might, in the course of a single interaction with passers-by, include informal conversation, a mini lecture about Jupiter’s moons, or a discussion about the formation of the Moon’s craters. The multimodal interaction may feature space-themed music played from a smartphone, a star-finding app, or an artistic photo posted to Instagram. All these interactions have taken place over the last decade of #popscope events, and some are suggested as possible forms of engagement in the #popscope manual ([#popscope, 2017](#)). All represent multiple ways of learning, teaching, and thinking.

5. Joyful and fun

Within the framework of informal or free-choice learning, there is ample room for joy, both for the #popscope volunteer and for the public. #popscope seeks to dissolve divisions between “teacher” and “learner” as much as possible while creating a non-judgemental, joyful space that rewards curiosity. In fact, the volunteer manual references “fun” three times, describing spontaneous #popscope events as fun and spontaneous, and reminds volunteers to share “both fun and serious” facts. The manual also instructs volunteers to “Sleep and dream about how much fun community astronomy is!” ([#popscope, 2017](#)). This element of joy is reflected in the spontaneous pop-up style of its events: [Buxner et al. \(2021, p. 148\)](#) refer to #popscope events as a “flashmob.” Volunteers are reminded #popscope should be fun: “If it starts to feel like work, stop.”

On this point, there is a resonance with the educational philosophy of John Dewey and his thoughts about the role of joy, and fun, and experiential learning in the classroom ([Dewey, 1916](#)) as well as contemporary literature on joy in educational spaces, including Black joy in Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics (STEM) fields ([Worsley & Roby, 2021](#)). A review of #popscope guests’ facial reactions from #popscope events ([#popscope, 2025b](#)) shows a range of positive facial expressions and body language that suggest joy ([Mortillaro & Dukes, 2018](#)), including smiling, hugging one another, and open arms. In addition to the intrinsic value of experiencing joy, it has an important pedagogical function. Experiences of joy, like other positive emotions such as awe, wonder, hope, and pleasure, can positively impact learning outcomes and learner experiences (e.g., [Rantala & Määttä, 2012](#); [McPhetres, 2019](#); [Cronqvist, 2021](#); [Huang, 2022](#)).

5.1 Meeting strangers: intimacy and lessons from house music. Meeting neighbours and inviting passers-by are at the core of the #popscope experience, which creates spontaneous connections and social intimacy. The manual, for example, describes “[Inviting] passers-by” as “the best part!” ([#popscope, 2017](#)). The manual also reminds volunteers to be assertive, inclusive, and friendly. [Panico \(2016\)](#) interviewed one #popscope volunteer who noted that “Folks walking by might stop with the intention of a quick peek through a telescope but end up staying much longer” and shared personal stories ([para 5](#)). The joy of connecting with strangers in a spontaneous space is linked in the literature to another form of public gathering: dance. The founders of #popscope were strongly influenced by their time spent on house music dance floors and were thrilled by its possibilities. House music (e.g., [Klangkarussell, 2014](#); [Perevedentseva & Garcia, 2016](#)) has been described as radically inclusive, intimate, joyful and even spiritual ([Garcia, 2011](#)). Like house music, there is a group “intimacy” and “togetherness” among strangers ([Garcia, 2011, p. 12](#)) generated by the common experience of looking through a telescope.

#popscope’s emphasis on collective, spontaneous joy has much in common with documented experiences of collective joy in large astronomy events or phenomena, such as during solar

eclipses. In a scale study of over 2 million Twitter (now X) messages sent during the 2017 solar eclipse in the United States, [Goldy et al. \(2022, p. 1452\)](#) found that, compared to users outside the eclipse path, users inside the path “exhibited more awe and expressed less self-focused and more prosocial, affiliative, humble, and collective language.” More than that, they found that these users used more “prosocial, affiliative, humble, and collective language” than they did before the eclipse ([Goldy et al., 2022, p. 1452](#)).

According to [Baron \(2017\)](#), people who witnessed this event appeared to be psychologically aligned. The eclipse offered the chance to connect with other people across differences, preferences, and political allegiances. Baron describes how the 2017 eclipse could bring people together and benefit individual and community well-being: “In this age of polarised politics, siloed entertainment, and individualised news feeds, the eclipse offered a precious shared experience – one that lifted and joined rather than debased and divided” ([p. 242](#)).

6. Affinity spaces, public “third” spaces and public spaces

“Affinity spaces” may be a useful frame to theoretically tie all the elements of #popscope pedagogy together discussed so far: access and equity, informality, use of digital tools, joy and public connectedness. Affinity spaces are “passion-based, out-of-school teaching and learning systems, organised in ways that are quite different from and foreign to schools” ([Gee, 2004, pp. 85–87](#); [O’Shea, 2018](#)) and are a valuable addition to our understanding of formal and informal spaces. Spaces, like the ones #popscope created on street corners ([Figure 4](#)), are even less formal than informal science spaces as described in the literature (e.g., [Falk et al., 2007](#); [Plummer & Small, 2013](#)), and, as a result, offer unique opportunities for engaging the public. Informal, affinity spaces include “multiple routes to participation,” “distributed knowledge,” and “everyone [sharing] lots of interests and knowledge” ([Gee, 2004, p. 89](#)). These spaces, which allow for unexpected and informal interactions with community members, are both rare and more important in an age of declining membership in civic associations (e.g., [Putnam, 2000](#); [Skocpol, 2013](#)), greater political polarisation (e.g., [Dolman et al., 2023](#)), decreasing faith in formal institutions, and greater anxiety and isolation among adolescents.

Critical scholars such as [Galvan \(2001\)](#), [Phillips \(2006\)](#), [Haddix et al. \(2016\)](#) and others recognise much learning that happens in informal spaces such as the kitchen table, the church steps, and the apartment courtyard. These are often gendered and racialised spaces that are typically “considered too personal and not rigorous enough” in traditionally male-dominated academia ([Galvan, 2001, p. 606](#)). Instead, informal spaces should be analysed as real pedagogical spaces for many underprivileged groups.

Affinity spaces, third spaces, and informal learning spaces are less hierarchical and inherently less formal than formal school environments. Both the internal organisation of #popscope itself and its outreach philosophy aspire to be non-hierarchical and democratic. For example,

Figure 4 Conceptualising interactions at #popscope event as an example of an affinity space. In this representation of a typical #popscope event, a variety of guests (blue) and volunteer organizers (pink) engage with one another in a variety of ways and with the telescope (pointed at the Moon) as they activate an urban public space over the course of an evening. Dotted lines represent more ephemeral interactions; solid lines are stronger, long-term social relationships.

Multiple routes to participation and diffuse leadership

Figure 5 Engaging with #popscope as an example of an affinity space. The dotted line denotes a porous relationship between in-person and online activities.. Model adapted from Gee, 2004 (pp. 86-87).

while some volunteers lead #popscope chapters and others are more active, there is no formal hierarchy in the group, and consensus among volunteers is always the goal during decision-making. #popscope's outreach is similarly philosophically oriented ([Figure 5](#)). Although there are #popscope volunteers with formal astronomy backgrounds, many do not. This feature of the organisation's volunteers, in addition to broadening the umbrella of amateur astronomy, helps with public engagement. In our experience, friendly conversation and collaborative co-learning maintain guests' attention far better than a street-corner lecture, and lead to deeper learning. In an instance where, during a #popscope event, neither a guest nor a volunteer knows the nature of a bright object shining in the western sky, they could work together and use their phones to discover that the object is, for example, the reddish star Arcturus. In this way, #popscope volunteers seek not to lecture the public, but rather create a space where astronomy co-learning can take place (e.g., [Azevedo, 2019](#)), knowledge is shared, and relationships are formed. At #popscope events, volunteers are excited about what can be learned together in an experiential, non-hierarchical learning environment (e.g., [Dewey, 1916](#); [Freire, 2020](#)).

Affinity spaces could take place in a variety of places outside of traditional school settings (online and in-person settings; [Gee, 2004](#)), including the public, urban spaces that are a pillar of the #popscope mission. One of the goals of #popscope is the social activation of urban public spaces ([#popscope, 2025a](#)) and the realisation of their role as sites of community mixing and social capital formation. #popscope pedagogy and the affinity spaces ([Gee, 2004](#); [O'Shea, 2018](#)) described may thus represent a type of "third space" or "place" (e.g., [Soja, 1989](#); [Oldenburg, 1999](#); [Table 1](#)). Third spaces (or places) are neither places for work nor employment; they are more inclusive sites of "sociability, spontaneity, community building and emotional expressiveness", and essential for society ([Jeffres et al., 2009](#)). Though the boundaries between home, work, and informal civic spaces may have blurred (e.g., [Soja, 1989](#)) with labour market changes and shift to online socialisation that intensified during the lockdowns of COVID-19, third spaces help describe the feelings and social value (individually and collectively) of bumping into neighbour on the street or café ([Simões Aelbrecht, 2016](#)), jumping into a pick-up basketball game, or joining friends at a place of worship.

These third spaces also include sidewalks (e.g., [Jacobs, 1992](#); [Mehta & Bosson, 2010](#); [Loukaitou-Sideris & Ehrenfeucht, 2011](#)), public parks (e.g., [Low et al., 2005](#); [Peters, 2010](#)), and informal green spaces (e.g., [Sikorski et al., 2021](#)). [Simões Aelbrecht \(2016\)](#) goes further and adds "fourth spaces" for our consideration, which are theoretically linked to third spaces as informal sites of social mixing. These include "private businesses of cafés, shops and all other informal gathering spaces in the city, including street intersections, stoops, edge spaces, bus stops and waiting spaces" ([p. 125](#)). In short, third and fourth spaces are fertile grounds for the kind of spontaneous, non-hierarchical public interaction that drives learning in affinity spaces and are the ingredients for a successful #popscope event.

Features of a #popscope event, with characteristics of affinity spaces
Access to telescope is democratised
Knowledge is shared; everyone learns together
Low barriers to entry to events, which are public and free
Minimal hierarchies and porous leadership structures
Guests may become volunteers at future events
Brought together by common interest
Many forms and routes to participation

Table 1 #popscope as affinity space: Adapted from [Gee \(2004, pp. 85-87\)](#).

7. Discussion

Spaces beyond the classroom, including informal spaces and affinity spaces, are not panaceas to the inequities and challenges observed in formal schooling. [Berman \(2020\)](#), for example, notes the tendency to sometimes overly romanticise informal learning spaces as ideal, completely democratic spaces. Informal learning spaces can reproduce some of the same systemic barriers as formal learning, as was observed in the [Buckland et al. \(2020\)](#) study of #popscope's outreach activities in one highly segregated American city. Using a critical geography lens, the researchers found that #popscope's outreach activities, though reaching a wide swath of the city's communities and demographics, did not reach all neighbourhoods equally, despite intentional attempts to serve neighbourhoods with fewer educational and astronomy education resources. How volunteers were recruited and sustained – and their relationship to volunteers' existing social circles – may be one contributing factor to this phenomenon, but more research is needed.

[Gee \(2004\)](#) also cautions about the applicability of informal affinity spaces to formal classroom environments since the latter are inherently institutional; there is an "inherent contradiction" ([O'Shea, 2018, p. 4](#)). Nevertheless, both [Gee \(2004\)](#) and [O'Shea \(2018\)](#) point out that classroom teachers should look to features of informal and affinity spaces, such as

those #popscope creates, that engage and motivate learners – including marginalised and racialised students – in ways that traditional classrooms may not. An example of introducing informal education could include organising a solar observing day outside the school as part of a physics curriculum, in which students try out and test different types of telescopes and solar filters. Introducing elements of affinity spaces could be starting a student-led after school astronomy club or supporting students to host their own community sidewalk astronomy event, perhaps in collaboration with a library, maker space or local amateur astronomy organisation. Digital spaces (such as a student-led astronomy TikTok channel or WhatsApp thread) could complement these activities and allow for the kind of “multiple routes to participation” and “distributed knowledge” typical of affinity spaces ([Gee, 2004, p. 89](#)). In fact, #popscope has helped support the creation of two after-school astronomy clubs at two high schools in the urban school districts of Chicago and Philadelphia.

Sidewalk astronomy is not a replacement for a high school astronomy or physics class; however, it may energise the reluctant learner in a physics course or engage the student in school who does not have access to high-quality, pre-college science and math courses. Such courses are inequitably distributed across school districts in the United States by race, income, language level, and other student characteristics. For example, of majority Black or Hispanic schools, only 66% offered Chemistry and 74% offered Algebra 2 ([McNeil & Blad, 2014](#)), both of which are foundational for taking college-level STEM courses. Advanced Placement courses, the most popular mechanism for students to earn college credit in the United States, are also inequitably distributed: “Black and Indigenous students are more likely to enrol in schools offering fewer AP courses” ([Chatterji et al., 2021, p. 37](#)). Moreover, even when AP (Advanced Placement) courses are available at a high school, Black Latinx, and Indigenous students face greater systemic barriers to accessing and succeeding in AP courses compared to their white and Asian peers (p.1). Across both resourced and under-resourced school districts, few high schools offer astronomy (e.g., [Krumenaker, 2010](#)). Students without access to robust high school science and math offerings or opportunities to earn college-level math and science coursework are at a distinct disadvantage when applying to and succeeding in STEM majors at the undergraduate university level and beyond, compounding disparities in representation in STEM careers, including astronomy.

Given this landscape of inequities in the classroom, affinity spaces, like those #popscope creates, offer opportunities outside the classroom for students and the public at large to learn about astronomy and delve deeper into related topics such as calculus or even photography. We also note that the risk of spreading pseudoscience or misinformation, especially in astronomy (e.g., [Impey, 2024](#)), is real, and guests sometimes bring up astrology, UFOs, or question the Moon landings when approaching our telescope. However, #popscope volunteers often use these questions as springboards to talk about astronomy (e.g., “Did you know that Gemini, the Zodiac sign, is also a constellation of stars [...] and it is right above you?”), to encourage the guest to think more deeply about a question (e.g., “Why did you think the Moon landings were

fake?”). They might explore the science of optics in such a situation: “No, actually with this magnification of this telescope, we would not be able to see the flag on the Moon. Do you have questions about the telescope’s optics and how it works?”. Learning together with the public, therefore, does not mean “anything goes” in conversations about astronomy and science, and the same is true for other affinity spaces. We are in pursuit of learning and truth together. This aspect of #popscope pedagogy connects to the fundamental elements of affinity spaces, where teaching and learning take place, but in ways that are “quite different” or look unfamiliar to traditional schooling ([Gee, 2017, p. 27](#)).

8. Conclusion

To theorise the teaching, learning, and organisation that form part of a #popscope pedagogy, this manuscript has drawn connections between #popscope’s practised mission (spreading astronomy knowledge, connecting people, activating public spaces) on one hand, and educational theories and literature on the other. #popscope pedagogy may be best described as a transformative (and joyful), hybrid, multimodal, community-rooted, anti-hierarchical teaching and learning approach that seeks to centre the margins and to embrace democratic astronomy and public spaces. Identifying elements of #popscope pedagogy helps distil and theorise the shared teaching and learning practices of a large volunteer-based informal science group that has grown and evolved since its founding in 2014. As a pedagogy rooted in community building, democracy and public spaces, #popscope provides a critical addition to the discourse on informal and formal science learning. The inclusive style of internal and organisation and equity-driven choice of sites are important pedagogical decisions that necessarily shape the teaching and learning that takes place at #popscope events.

#popscope, or its approach, is not a fix-all to inequities inside the classroom, including inequitable access to robust STEM courses, but it offers alternative learning pathways that may also appeal to those learners not engaged in or marginalised by the traditional classroom. Both social astronomy ([Bará, 2009](#)) and affinity spaces, a type of non-traditional, non-hierarchical learning space theorised by Gee ([2004; 2017](#)), offer a valuable framework for connecting and explaining the elements of #popscope pedagogy. These elements include access and equity, informal or free-choice learning, hybrid in-person and online learning, and joy. This pedagogy and practice may be a best practice for other sidewalk astronomy groups seeking to engage with urban communities and spaces in mutually sustaining ways. The author looks forward to education researchers, science educators, and amateur astronomers (including those within #popscope) alike reflecting on this research, considering its practical implications, and building on its findings.

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Notes

1. #popscope’s approach does not diminish the importance of introducing the public to the wonders of a dark sky site or the urgent work of dark sky preservation (e.g., [DarkSky International, 2025](#)), but rather complements those essential efforts. A trip to a dark sky site might take weeks or months to organise, if a member of the public is aware of or able to participate in the trip in the first place. In the meantime, #popscope can provide immediate access for a city-dwelling guest to the night sky through public telescope viewing. Even in light-polluted downtown Chicago (Bortle Class 9), we have shown guests the lunar craters and Jupiter’s moon – which often prompt conversations about urban light pollution.

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